

Magical South. An eight-bullet-point photoshoot¹ of everyday life in the tourist city

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Abstract:

Magical South is a major detour around my own island, taking a road between urban enclaves in which the popular dynamics of neighbourhoods rub up against and collide with the 'tourist bubble', the prototypical closed space for tourism removed from the local. This theoretical 'photoshoot' of sorts endeavours to disclose the unconsciousness in operation when we cross through the tourist city, imbued in a semiotics that recreates a time, repetitions and a chaotic visual mesh. It begins with Walter Benjamin's appraisal of the mechanism that enables copies to continue facilitating motivation for tourist travel. This returns us to the *detour* without detracting from the critique of the bunkerization of the city through processes like gentrification, paying attention to how everyday violence also runs through ordinary affects and the mainstream banality created by tourism.

Keywords: film, tourist bubble, everyday life, tactility and distraction, uncanny, gentrification.

¹ Except for pictures 2 and 4, which are taken from the Internet from unknown authors, the remaining photographs are by the author of this essay.

What, at the end, makes advertising so superior to criticism? Not what the moving red neon says – but the fiery pool reflecting it in the asphalt.

Walter Benjamin

I

Photo 1

To burst the ‘tourist bubble’, a form of consuming the city predicated on closed spaces, Dean MacCannell takes a certain distance from authors like Mike Davis, who depicted Los Angeles as an area fragmented into highly regulated hermetic spaces obsessed with security. MacCannell takes an approach more akin to the city’s *unconsciousness* and begins with Walter Benjamin’s *Diaries*, written during his time in Moscow, to capture a different urban dynamic:

What fullness has this street that overflows not only with people, and how deserted and empty is Berlin! In Moscow goods burst everywhere (...). Every fifty steps stand women with cigarettes, women with fruit, women with sweets (...). Next to them are sugar figures, nuts, candy... Picture books lie in the snow; Chinese sell artfully made paper fans, and still more frequently, paper kites made in the form of exotic deep sea fish ... Shoe polish and writing materials, handkerchiefs, doll’s sleighs, swings for children, ladies underwear, stuffed birds, clothes hangers—all this sprawls on the open street, as if it were not twenty-five degrees below zero (cited in MacCannell, 2011: 103).

‘This is not the “Toys R Us” version of the commodity,’ MacCannell tells us. No. It is an odd report from a Marxist from the very ‘heart of the revolution’ to gauge the pulse of the behaviour of commodities in an economy other than one driven by capital. The scene reminds me of an episode of *The Simpsons* when Lisa gets lost after boarding the wrong bus and ends up bewildered in a Russian quarter. In a short space of time all sorts of objects are pushed in her face, invading her safe space. For MacCannell, this street spectacle denotes another form of operating with things: there is a surplus value besides use and exchange values; therefore, commodities unfold beyond their spectral corset within the capitalist market and have a symbolic value while at once being almost magically magnetic. But, are these qualities of the commodity exclusive to the streets of Moscow, in some backwater not only of capitalist cycles but also of State legality? Do we have to be so far out on the edge to experience objects as ‘flourishing’? Dating back to the 1960s, many theses on the consumer society argued in a different way, saying that

the tendency to express sign and symbol values are the new statute of fetishization of the commodity following World War II. And even earlier, in the incipient era of technological reproduction and the advent of cinema and advertising, Benjamin already perceived this quality on the streets of Paris, in its arcades, in collections and, I would even dare to venture, in the materials of his own diaries, in a dainty blue book, saying that ‘others compare it to shoes from Turkistan’ (cited in Taussig, 2012: 6).

For the time being, Benjamin has been conscripted for the design of future tourist cities. But he has also been critical, however indirectly, in drawing up a theory on tourist attraction to destinations. Benjamin begins his celebrated essay on the mechanical reproduction of images by speaking of a change in level that took place around 1900 which affects the ‘aura’, the here and now, both of natural landscapes and works of art. The copy ‘enables the original to meet the beholder halfway’ (see Benjamin, 2005) and will create a feeling of attraction towards tourist destinations, like the Canary Islands in that early period.

II

Consider an image taken in Red Square in Moscow around 1996, which shows a big signboard with ‘Canarias’ as a logo offering the destination, while in the square some demonstrators are seen with USSR flags. Consider the ability for ‘Canarias’ to travel to faraway places, to cold and ideologically adverse places. One has to bear in mind that the photo was taken at a pivotal moment, at a time when the alternative economy that Benjamin saw flourishing in Moscow had long since ground to a halt. The Berlin Wall had fallen and someone had announced the ‘end of history’. Images, and copies, meet faraway beholders more than halfway to foster desire. And that meant something ‘new’ in perception. It is not as if the former USSR had not seen the experience of mechanical reproduction analysed by Benjamin, rather that here it bursts on the scene, with a jouissance of sorts, almost like a symptom through which the whole libidinal economy of an already late capitalism penetrated (Santa Ana, 2012). Here tourism is accepted as the most appropriate vehicle to convey its logic to new accumulations. The Canarias’ history with this is convoluted, but we should now ask ourselves what kind of perception we have in the non-copied terrain; which is to say, not in the moving image of fantasy, but in the very material place of those mass hallucinations.

III

Photo 2

It would be a mistake to presuppose from the outset that signs are now further removed from their referents, or that the Canary Islands retain something foreign to the images

reproduced of them. However, this is one of the spiritual reserves that some tourism theorists safeguard in their mappings of tourist motivation. They accept that something real is separated from the image: is this because destinations are still perceived as authentic? In one sense, this theory of tourism seems to turn Benjamin's thesis on its head: namely, copies are not detrimental to the aura of the original, but in fact *magnify* it. Other visions, more accommodating with postmodernism, formulate the question differently: if the world is already completely hyperreal, if we already accept that we are enmeshed in simulacra and representations, then why do people travel to other places?ⁱ But, starting with his seminal text on mechanical reproduction, the German philosopher also left us one of the most enigmatic and difficult contributions to respond to the unknowns of tourist motivation beyond this simple inversion and beyond a capitulation to a world consisting of simulacra. To my way of thinking, this contribution could be coupled with a short story by the Canarian writer Alonso Quesada, written before Benjamin's decisive interventions on the new 'optical unconscious'.

The main shift in the new perceptiveness is that it is not just a case of what the eye perceives as vision, but a tactile adjunct that thickens the plot; and which, in my mind, should also complicate the theoretical assumptions based on the ocularcentrism that cuts across tourism studies. Tourism is of course a multidimensional phenomenon, and perhaps there are some categories of tourists that still view themselves as 'contemplators' of landscapes and works of art, not to mention striking up meaningful (in contradistinction to fleeting and dishonest) relations with the host people. Yet, generally speaking, mass tourism is more a question of a 'distracted' gaze. Distraction is not a vice of low culture, but rather the new perceptiveness enabled by advances in capitalism in the late-nineteenth century. Its flipside, contemplation, is a direct engagement with the landscape or artwork, imbuing the spectator in a kind of adoration: a connection with unique things, with God. Distraction is more a peripheral vision that eschews being alone with God in order to situate itself in the urban masses of any city, in frantic motion, in the assembly line and, of course, in film and advertising. And these are the most tactile elements of all! Film and advertising produce a strange synaesthesia. Addressing this Benjaminian argument strikes me as highly difficult, but it unquestionably hovers over my observations of tourism's insistence in offering sensorial experiences beyond the gaze that dominates the practice. Tourism is construed as a desire induced by travel images, to things we later get to touch, listen to and taste. And afterwards to be preserved in images taken there, in the destination. That being said, in this whole process, if we agree with the argument that we are trying to clarify, is it not true that we have always looked with the sense of touch? And is it no less true that memory involves the whole body and not just a mental image?

IV

Image and touch pointed the way for Michael Taussig to mimesis and its modern history in anthropology.ⁱⁱ Benjamin had already told us about the mimetic faculty and language, from those onomatopoeic cultures who looked to the skies. Yet what can we say about the mimesis of the new machinery of reproduction? These machines are what

reveal the optical unconscious, but this is not a secular road that quickly leads the photography camera or the phonograph to the take-off runway of modernism. On the other hand, if we take tactility and the image into consideration, it would be hard for us to disassociate them from the types of magic accepted in so-called primitive societies. James Frazer contended that there are two types of magic: *contagion* (of things that are related to other things: like the hair or nail clippings used in magic spells) and *imitation* (of things similar to other things: images, photos, dolls, drawings that affect whoever the image corresponds to). These are, we might say, the principles of copy and substance in reproduction technology around our modern world. The ‘physiognomic aspects of visual worlds,’ as Benjamin put it. Taussig added a key quote from the latter to capture this meeting point: ‘Every day the urge grows stronger to get hold of an object at very close range by way of its likeness, its reproduction.’ (Taussig, 1993: 20) Once again, touch connecting the two parts of sympathetic magic.

The image of the giant orange faucet in the Water Park in the south of Tenerife plays with a kind of popular magic, closer to a magician sawing in two his assistant locked inside a box than to spells cast using the basic principles described by Frazer. It is more like the optical magic that makes you believe that there is something where there is none. That being said, the magic of tourism is, at once, an imitation of that; but only to return to nothingness: it is making you believe that there is something authentic (an optical illusion) that you can touch (authentic) before realizing that not only was it not there (it was just a staged authenticity) but that you had touched it visually (like cynical tourists enjoying the artificialness of what they are visiting). Tourism imitates the destination on top of the actual existing destination, but is driven by a fascination with what is lost precisely in copying; an issue that speaks to the anomic structures of capitalism and the search for authenticity that gives meaning to our detraditionalized identities. Benjamin said that mechanical reproduction broke with tradition and this assertion is basic for understanding how tourism threads together its own narrative.

V

Photo 3

Is the unconscious closer to the tourist city than the latter is to the erstwhile working areas now mutilated by multinationals or the new spaces enclosed in a kind of bunkerization obsessed with security? MacCannell himself does not rule out Davis’s critique (which analyses this sense of the militarization of the urban space), but tries to ensure that the city does not seem numbed without this kind of unconscious, to which major diversions would have to be added. Benjamin’s synaesthesia unquestionably has a lot to offer, even beyond its expansion of the values of commodities from his observations on Moscow. It is on the street and in everyday life where an optical unconscious grounded in the peripheral vision of distraction comes into play. What happens when you saturate the space of neon signs for tourism, when everything exceeds normality? What happens when all this imitates the ego, but it turns out that

this ego *is* a tourist ego? I am thinking about my strolls around Punta Brava, a poor neighbourhood on the outskirts of the tourist city of Puerto de la Cruz, a very important detour for me. Without a doubt, all the neighbourhood's tourist elements are mixed up with what a neighbourhood supports as a neighbourhood: the Guanche street names alongside billboards for Loro Park, signs for closed bars like Calypso, stickers with 'messages from God', vertical advertising for Brunelli's steakhouse or signage with species of fishing interest in the Canaries. The thing is that I did not even notice the street names nor the omnipresence of Loro Park, the Canaries' foremost theme park, situated inside the neighbourhood like a tourist bubble. Did I not notice them because they were too evident, almost like touching them with the vision? And so, here, the bunker and everyday life coexist, everything in my optical unconscious, in my mainstream banality.

Something uncanny, as Freud would have it, lurks in these walkabouts. The reporter, art historian and walker Mariano de Santa Ana bears witness to as much when he writes that 'one needs a lot of training to learn to look at the city itself, to excavate in the image that resides in our eyes, where we do not nor cannot reside' (Santa Ana, 2019: 121). How strange this idea of the residency of an image in the eye, somewhere we cannot be, but where we unquestionably touch. I do not presume to see in my friend Mariano outdated theories on light and its human receptacle, but I do intuit that he himself has thought that the city is not only touched on seeing it, but that it is also transubstantiated with the body, something even more uncanny. Is this why he quotes John Donne: 'I am the Babylon that I must go out of'? Mariano, the reporter who strolls absent-mindedly about Las Palmas, alerted me to a text by Alonso Quesada, the old distracted contemplator of the same city, an 'intelligent Atlantic man' connected with early-twentieth century British colonial society. Mariano says that Quesada did not know the phase of mass tourism, but that, in his short story called 'Sirenas yankees', he was able to capture the filmic unconscious that the tourist already encapsulated:

A voice cried out: 'Tourists! Tourists! Ah, truly we knew of their arrival! Yes, Yankee tourists. An agency from New York turned its building into a boat. How have we forgotten? Six hundred dollars, from New York to Italy. One day in the Canaries, another day in the Azores and then half a day in the Iberian provinces. Half a day in Madrid, half a day in Barcelona. *The world in cinematograph, but with the film reflected outwards. It was the audience who quickly turned in front of this screen of the impassive world.* (cited in Santa Ana, 2012: italics added)

Written a few decades before Benjamin penned his famous essay on mechanical reproduction and his thoughts on cinema and photography, this fragment ought to attract the attention of Benjaminian scholars who focus on tactility and distraction. But even more so, it ought to serve the purposes of the age-old question of tourism studies: What is the sense of tourism in a hyperreal world where copy and original coalesce in a Matrix made solely of simulacra? What can we say when the film, the source of simulacra, is reflected outwards? Is this not already the world of simulacra? Are we unable now to unravel the loose and hackneyed separation between the fiction of the

image and the substance of the real? Mariano says that, with these steps in tourism, 'history accelerates, the real collapses.' I now feel like inside a turbine of postmodern ideas that ostensibly vanished a while back or were assigned to the annals of the space of theorization within which we thought that history lost itself forever. Yet now history seems not only to have returned with renewed strength, but, in addition, repositions itself along the lines it left back in 1989, with a confrontation between Russia and NATO that could have biblical proportions. And along with history, it seems that the real has returned too. Mariano quotes Paul Virilio: 'with acceleration, to travel is like filming.' In fact, Quesada had taken it a step further: film and tourism make a strange montage in which everyday life is subsumed within the optical unconscious. Virilio himself also believed as much when he quoted the video artist Nam June Paik: 'The cinema isn't I see, it's I fly.' Let us now consider it in relation with war, which is what Virilio (see 1989) studied, the importance of the visual capacity to locate the enemy and so destroy him. Furthermore, let us think of this with the new technology currently deployed in warfare, with drones and highly sophisticated applications. Is there an optical unconscious of war also informed by the technologies employed in it? Is there a kind of evil magic of contagion and imitation in operating this technology?

VII

By turning the camera, by projecting everything outwards like making a *GraffMapping* avant la lettre, Quesada understood the early key to tourist motivation: film is outside; cinema is a technology of contact and substance, just like old magic. Tourism is cinema, and cinema is tourism. And, the anthropologist David Picard would add, tourism is magic. The quote that Mariano made me see and touch deserves to be included in *The Arcades Project*, like a quote interconnected to other elements of Benjamin's extensive atlas. But there is also another dimension that Quesada kept in mind (counting the days and half days) and which unquestionably affects film and tourism: the dimension of time.ⁱⁱⁱ

Photo 4

It is widely believed that you cannot perceive time with the senses, but unquestionably we feel and create a new temporal experience with early-twentieth century reproduction technologies like cinema. Not only do they capture moments, or freeze images with photography, but something of their flow also becomes part of our own everyday flow (of how we understand the passing of time).^{iv}

At this juncture, we have to think on various levels. Benjamin received film's entry into the modern as a force emancipating us from time and the space in which city planning contains us: 'Then came the film and burst this prison-world asunder by the dynamite of the tenth of a second' (Benjamin, 2005). But, first of all, it needs to be agreed that film and advertising create cultural products that adapt their temporality to technological

limitations and to what is stipulated as necessary within the framework of consumerism. This is patent in societies contingent precisely on capitalist consuming: advertisements and films have an estimated duration so that the consumer can coexist with the other temporalities that mark their lives at work and in leisure (with the exception of eight-hour films of people sleeping by Andy Warhol!). At the same time, beyond their content and symbolization, films and advertising induce a notion of time: we add a temporal unconscious to our optical unconscious. And this is something that has changed with different cultural formats. The storyteller, the written novel, radio, film and, finally, television series in the age of Internet have informed us about time and how to experience it in different ways. What changes now, in this latest digital phase, is that these new technologies allow us to live our everyday lives and to continue being able to follow a long plot (as if the story did not have to be compressed into little over two hours, but that it almost overlaps with our own living time). Today we do not rush to experience tourism limited to the duration of a standard film (a holiday trip); but now, converted into the hyperbolic tourist advanced by Warhol, filming and photographing non-stop (Santa Ana, 2012), we live in *our own* TV series (a two-pronged approach: on one hand, we fictionalize ourselves, and, on the other, the series we watch, generally ones classified as ‘high-quality’, can avoid clichés because they have more time to develop characters; there are no hurried conclusions; and they focus on details which at times lead nowhere, adding a level of realism increasingly more overlapping with our everyday lives).

Photo 5

But at the destination, like anywhere in the world, time changes things as they are, as if those things were sandcastles, with their fragility and non-defined temporality, something that spurs tourism more in search of a frozen image than a film. It is true that the leisure industry renews and changes its tired clichés for new formulas, but this has nothing to do with the dynamics of local change, but rather with the expectations of global consumerism that seeks in self-referentiality the spice or *melange* of postmodern tourism (Rothman, 1998: 340). Tourism, driven by nostalgia, seeks a timeless time, a souvenir, a frozen death that can only be captured as such by film and advertising, or by the often mass reproduced figurine, like a copy of something original from the place (Estévez, 2019).

VIII

And how do native people experience time in places frozen in nostalgia? What montages would we prefer for our lives in the midst of all this stasis which is now our future? William Burroughs felt increasingly more trapped in the local during his trip to Ecuador in search of ayahuasca, experiencing a kind of panic: ‘Every morning a swelling cry goes up from the kids who sell Luckies in the street— “A ver, Luckies’. Look here Luckies”—Will they still be saying “A ver, Luckies” a hundred years from

now? Nightmare fear of stasis. Horror of being finally *stuck* in this place' (Burroughs, 2007: 56). Do we feel panic when faced with the scenario for tourism, that 'screen of the *impassive* world'? The stillness instigated by tourism is a repetition we are unconscious of; a scenario that is repeated for desire. Something so still is not like a movie, with all its footage in motion. It is more like the film still, a fixed image, like the panic-stricken stasis. (To my way of thinking, panic is like seeing something still and familiar but completely divested of all meaning, what is usually described in anxiety attacks as a sensation of hallucinating while fully awake, but which is in fact reality itself, without any symbolic dressing or underpinning).

But, as Kathleen Stewart tells us, a still can also be 'a machine hidden in the woods that distils spirits into potency through a process of slow condensation.' What work a still is capable of! The writer reinforces her claim with painting, which captures the aliveness of supposedly inanimate objects. It is also frequent in cinema, like in Hitchcock when he wishes to create suspense, or, to give another example: in Scorsese, when, by pausing the flow of images he creates a still that unleashes a plethora of narrative possibilities. 'Ordinary life, too, draws its charge from rhythms of flow and arrest. Still life punctuate its significance.'

'So still, like a postcard' says Stewart (2007: 18-19). For those of us who live in a postcard it is obvious that tourism punctuates our significance, but we do not allow ourselves to be so easily entrapped by stasis, though at times we are prey to panic.

Photo 6

For Stewart, the banal elements of our everyday lives are the essential things with which to elaborate the 'ordinary affects' that shape the 'we' of mainstream banality: 'A world of shared banalities can be a basis of sociality [...] A weirdly floating "we" snaps into a blurry focus"' (Stewart, 2007: 27-28) There we are ... walking, strolling, distracted. How is it possible not to see the potentialities of stasis, of the still, interconnected with ordinary affects and, at the same time, with the optical and temporal unconscious that shows us a world crumbling like a sandcastle under the advancing tide? But this is the same punctuation that the (so still and repetitive) bubble gives to the significance of our lives outside of it. Is this some kind of new dialectics? Stewart says that the still image can also be 'an alibi for all of the violence, inequality and social madness folded into the open disguise of ordinary things.' Then I am not sure whether we are bursting the bubble or whether, on the other hand, we are living with it (or have been up until now). The question is that Mike Davis was not so far removed from Dean MacCannell in his judgement on the touristified (or gentrified) postmodern city. The former is cited by the latter to demonstrate the raw reality of the urban apocalypse in his opening words on Los Angeles in *City of Quartz*; but I would just like to paraphrase it, right now, to demonstrate something of the interdependence of tourism with the native on the unconscious and tactile planes. Imagine a book that begins with the following paragraph:

Going down the road from La Cisnera to Tajao, through the desert in the south of the island of Tenerife, at sunset, you can make out in the growing darkness the spotlights of the garbage dump in Arico, the red lights that crown the wind turbines and the over-lit coastline of the now obsolete port of Granadilla, almost as if it were an industrial city in some dystopian future. If we follow a stretch of the road further west, past the airport, we would arrive at what we call “El Sur”, the South, a world of fun and fantasy. It is as if this hedonist picturesque world were waiting in its wedding dress on the day when our neighbouring environs succumb to tourist development, something which had already started to happen, with mega-projects that take over the coast and unspoiled nature. Perhaps, right here, the best place to view the Canary Islands of the next millennium is from the ruins of its now abandoned alternative futures; from tourist ruins.

Photo 7

In fact, Davis has a book devoted to the contribution of Latino migrant people to the urban make-up of California, primordial in MacCannell's examples for rethinking the city beyond the tourist ego and US fascism.^v The book is called *Magical Urbanism* (Davis, 2001). I believe that this is what Mariano and I acknowledge when we are out for a stroll: a magical urbanism. This term would probably have also been to the liking of Benjamin, who I imagine not now in the former USSR, but in today's 'tropicalized' spaces of mass tourism, where objects and city strive to survive the spell of gentrification. Commodities and other goods flourish under the urbanism of the *magical south* (and now not just in reference to the realism acclimatized in places near Colombia, but also the primal magic of contagion and imitation). Books of drawings (or photos of British football, like the ones I once came across) are burning under the sun outside a tourist complex. On the verge of becoming trash thanks to the excess of an economy in search of the sun, the objects hang on in, maintaining an uncanniness in their familiarity, carefully protecting their values of exchange, use, sign and symbol cupped in their hands...so that they don't suddenly jump away like restless grasshoppers.

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Notes

ⁱ See the doctoral dissertation by Chris Rojek (1991).

ⁱⁱ After this point, I follow his observation on tactility and mimesis in the work of Benjamin (Taussig, 1993), adding to the puzzle another text to disentangle this difficult point made by the German philosopher: see Taussig (2007).

ⁱⁱⁱ In the words of Beatriz Sarlo: 'Images need *time*: so that we visually sweep a fixed shot; so that a long shot shows us time in its narrative unfolding; so that, as Benjamin put it, we could operate a "process of associations"'. There is a threshold of time that is essential in film; portions of time below this threshold destroy the possibility of meaning arising, both in classic and modern films, in Eisenstein or Ford, Godard, Jarmusch or Chantal Akerman.' In: (Sarlo, 2006: pp. 58-59).

^{iv} My reflections on time and cinema applied to tourism are largely based on a book by Mary Ann Doane (2002).

^v For instance, see the author's comment on the myths of Aztlán, the origins of the Aztecs, applied to Orange County, in the heart of bunkerized and reactionary California (MacCannell, 2007: pp. 169-178).